

Impact of Gold Mining Exploitation on Schools Attainment a Case of Upper Guinea

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Abstract: This paper aims to experiment with how gold mining exploitation impacts on junior high school attainment, pupils are introduced to gold mining exploitations in siguiri province particularly the kintinia district region of Kankan. The world's largest problems today are child mortality in mining exploitation zones and children leaving or abandoning education with no or less qualifications. Despite this due to poverty alleviations in Africa countries, parents are not able to support children's spending. To attain this purpose, we did a field investigation and collected some sample data as mixed gender employed in gold mining zones. However, the sample comprised 98 observations, high school's 70 pupils, and 28 pupils' parents. We used to collect quantitative primary data, questionnaires, and interviews. The findings show that mining activities contributed to the rural pupils; leaving schools with no or fewer qualifications become a scourge for humanity. We suggested that is one of the sources of inter or extern immigration to pupils' poor school attainment. These gaps recommended that schools responsible in kintinia and traditional leaders; Parents of pupils should be discussing with the local authorities policies to emphasize and see the importance of child's education and for ensuring the success of their children. We suggested that future research is basic on the schools where abandonment is abundant in favor of mining activities. To give an overview of positive mining impact activities, the national policy must insert the job market or help them find a job that is not carried out; For pupils who cheer up on the examination to enter the university; to preserve the health and against dangers in mining areas. The lack of practicing mining activities in emerging countries; These results illustrate that mining impact impregnates the hypothesis that on pupils' school attainment even in rural or urban. Besides, the findings of school attainment involvement in the district of Kintinia education policies have conversed about children abandoning study and endorsed by the director of education of the Kankan region to end dropout and delinquency in the educational system in the impacted region.

Keywords: Schools Attainment; Mining Exploitation Impact; Upper Guinea

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I. INTRODUCTION

Today, the province Siguiiri as well as certain country, is one of the most expensive province in Guinea, from lack of security to crimes, drug dealings, prostitution, homelessness, poor sanitation and food insecurity etc. Rury and Tamura (2019). The field investigation remark show the traditional activities, which are agriculture, fishing, and breeding, are not doing well like years before industrial mining. Kourouma (2023) Suitable agricultural land in terms of fertility and availability is running out. These, as well as other climate conditions like scarcity of rain are causing far lesser productivity per hectare compared to few decades back.

According to Rousell Cutter and Mackenzie Knowles (2020), showed that in some developing countries, education is based on the climate crisis; but in Guinea, most of population lives in rural areas so the poverty rate is 49.2 and 19.1%

for extreme poverty Magassouba(2003). Despite the richness of its basement in gold, the communities in Siguiiri, Kintinian, still behind in terms of access to basic social infrastructures. Less school's infrastructures. In addition, the results that UNESCO (2019) identified the behavior of pupils attendance School has become for young peoples a scourge for humanity in rural and even urban areas pupils abandoning schools without degree qualifications is one of the sources of internal immigration. Precisely, according to research findings by UNESCO on different countries' school attainment, the school abandoning rate in Africa-sub-Sahara was found 38 percent, for northern Africa and western Asia 72 percent, central and southern Asia 75 percent, and in Latin America and Caribbean 76 percent. However, in upper Guinea children without degree qualification has immigrated to gold mining natural exploitation as particularly given to siguiri upper Guinea region of kankan Kruger,(2007), Santos, (2014). Understanding this gaps, to fight against it scourge, this

article we aim to identify the sources of motivations of children leaving schools before getting a basic level. The question is What's motivating or encouraging pupils to attend schools? and What measures need to be taken to reduce or limit attainment in schools?

According to the ministry of plan (2018) the situation geographics of Guinea has a strategic position in the heart of ECOWAS and shares 3,400 km of border with the sub-region of Guinea. Its 320km long coastline, the country is rich in seafood and potentially, gas and petrol in prospect. Guinea is divided into four natural regions, which main cities are Kindia, Kankan, N'zérékoré, Labé. Guinea's gold is one of the best qualities, the value varies from 850 to 998% (20 -23.5 gram). The regions rich in gold in Guinea are: Upper Guinea (provincial capital Kankan) which is the biggest region in Guinea, it covers Kankan, Siguiiri, Mandiana, Dinguiraye, Kouroussa, and Kerouane, this region is the most regions rich in gold and diamond than the rest regions of country? Also dominate by intense activities of traditional mining extraction in that area 1(one) m³ of sediment contents is from 1g to 10g of gold. Middle Guinea Filaba covers Mamou, Faranah, in which 1m³ (one) of sediment content is from 0.42g to 3.8g of gold. °Coast of Guinea, region of Sierra-Fora, kindia, Mambia and Boké. Guinea education country brief january (2024) reports by World Bank noticed that the province of siguiiri because of gold mining existence in this area, schools enrolment rate still low due to the poverty alleviation; parents migrate to gold minning with child doing activities finding their well-being. Primary schools students completion for females student stood at 61;50%. However in 2016 schools' enrollment rate for males students was 40.50% and females at 25% labor force was 63.7% for men and 41.7% for female women. 30.4% of Guinean's women in 2018 were involved in making decision in the househod due to a wide varieties of educational challenges which demand immediately the attention for Guineans' Government and its partners. However; completion rate for secondary education reveals a considerable drop off with only 30.8% of girls and 39.3% boys. The same source indicates that a gender gap with 31% of females enrolling against 41% males.

A. An Overview on Guinea's Education

According to Wann (1999), noted that Guinea's education Historic period from the independence day to nowadays has gone through three periods. Since the colonial era; education was in the hands of colonial administration; focusing only on teaching French culture; French history and its social organization was not open to all french colonies; Indigenous were not allowed to enroll you had to be blessed by the colonial administration. Once Guinea held 1958 independence in 1958 year; then schools opened to all genders females and males. With the socialist regime, schools were in the Government's hands which provided all services; like building Schools' facilities; supplying pedagogical tools; schools' uniforms; student health problems; examinations, etc... "Education was free" In that period; if you failed an examination one time; the candidate was allowed to retake it as many times as he could and; when you graduated Government would provide you with a job. Later in (1984) with a new regime held by the military; economic system was changed from socialism to liberalism; many socio-economic sectors were privatized; privatization in the education sector many facilities for learning; training like professionals and universities were built Now a lot of them; are held by the private sector.

That is one of the sources of low level of students which depend on fewer teachers' qualifications. Unfortunately; this sector is not under real control; from the recruitment of teachers to reaching the pedagogical practice. A lot of private schools are not deeply involved in the children's education; only making money. In Guinea parents, make valuable, contributions to children's education by paying a lot of tuition in school fees. As well as, Barry. A (2009) shows that this is Similar to many countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, parents spend various fees. however, let's see all these expenses made by the parents, and the children in turn must honor successfully not to drop out of school. The support of institutions like the World Bank; IMF had engaged in important reform with the Guinea Government called the "Structural Adjustment Program Sectorial" (SAPS) that drives the privatization of many socio-economic sectors; but many challenges stand in Guineas' Education Sector. Socio-economic development must start from the bottom up, which is why we suggest that parents educate their children to help them develop better beforehand even if the means are limited but see education as important. Depiste, as far as, Kirumba- Chedié, and Sekwao (2000) remark that Without education, development will not occur. Only educated people can command the skills necessary for sustainable economic growth and a better quality of life.

B. Theoretical Framework

Schools by the way Oxford Language is defined as institutions for the education of children or going in a particular discipline. A school is both an educational institution and a building designed to provide learning spaces and learning environments for teaching students under direction of teachers; the system is formal for many countries which is sometimes a compulsory; this is not the case in Guinea as many sub-Saharan countries. In Guinea as in many countries education system is held by the Government and private sector; the levels of education and training are: primary school level since 6 years old to 12 years old; there are a few areas where nurseries; the lack of this first degree, Guinea education system is a gap that needs to be closed, school level is end by doing an exam to get the first degree graduation.

The secondary level: Moreover, the transition from primary school to secondary which is divided into two levels. The graduates from first level; First section takes four years (7th; 8th 9th; and 10th degree); also ending by taking secondary degree examination and being graduated move to high school level; So that also start from 11th; 12th and 13th degree then take an examination called candidate for high school level exams graduations goes to universities degree. In that examination; a lot of candidates fall and discourage leaves; the only decision they could take. (Deep stress). From the statistics of UNICEF on Guinea education; low educational attainment especially for girls is due to in part; relatively high levels of child marriage and early childbearing. The same report reveals that a child born in Guinea today will reach 37% of his/her potential; which is much lower than the average for Sub-Saharan African regions. One of the latest statistics shows that a country's wealth mainly consists of three types of capital.

➤ *Produced Capital*

That from abroad investment; donors' and other partners; they invest on factories; equipment and social infrastructures; Guinea government can use the mineral resource to finance many infrastructures

➤ *Natural Capital*

Which concerns farmers land and renewable and nonrenewable natural resources; that need to be rationally exploited without comprising future generation. That sector could be a factor to take or support big infrastructures like electricity damp; supply water help farmers etc.

➤ *Human Capital*

Measured the present value of future earning to labor force; that depends on the level of educational attainment; this is one of big challenges Guinea's education facing.

Many jobs that required a qualification Guineans could not take due to no or less qualifications which enterprise provided; only unskilled jobs. On April 2016 research gate net found that young people who left school without qualification were increased at risk of involvement in Juvenil Research done on CSR of impact of mining extraction on community's education living around in Siguiri province (Up of Guinea) It is appeared in the graphic the level of education and the reason of leaving schools for a sample of 150 residents Shortage of qualifying teachers and lack of teachers; many schools specially in the rural areas are impacting of the quality of education delivers

According to the report of UNESCO (UIS) reveal that primary school completion rate was at 56% in 2021 for girls and 27% for boys. The result of my investigation in Siguiri; with a sample of 150 Residents 80% of the resident are illiterate and 7% of in the sample have left schools; attract by artisanal mining. On this community; education attainment rate is 17% from primary to secondary. Lack of teachers; poor revenue of families or facilities cannot be only the main source of motivation for younger to abandon their education with no qualification. other factors can be a source of motivation; among of these;

➤ *We can tell that:*

- Teachers with poor qualification affect the quality of teaching
- Number of students in the classrooms when the class is crowded like in some urbans 80 students in the same class; pedagogical activities could be done correctly.
- Economic Barriers. The Budget for education in Guinea is very low it cannot cover all activities only 1% of national budget. The international standard is 20% of country budget.
- Mondialization that impacts the children mind by

comparing their life to developing countries student life.

- Mining activities attract younger; who become ambitious and wants to change social statuts as soon as possible by leaving himself and their families in the extreme poverty; the time they could take; seems to be long.
- After graduating; outlive discourage many youngers to continue their education; they prefer to find other ways for better life
- Lack of real politics to help students who have been graduated to get a job.

If you look through in the recent pass time about the result of high school degree candidate examination; and the student graduates in terms of employment much of them are having a stress because there is no unblocked way to get job in the working market

National examination results to have high school degree graduation to go to universities; this is a disastrous situation when the candidate fail twice at that examination which become harmful. The scores that candidate much get to have an admission for diploma graduation is starting from 10/20 until 20/20 scores; fail scores is under of these above.

II. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCHS

A quantitative method that gives more details on this research; it could allow us to compare; cross and transpose data. We have collected the data at four levels; national result; thesis on CSR of Guinea mining companies by authors Dr. Kourouma (2024) National statistics on Guinea education in the last seven years;(2018 to 2024) we built a table and graphics for explain by comparing the progress or recede; rate of abandoning education and failure impact of the bachelor examination (discourage).

III. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Gray et Al in (1978) Said that; analysis of the result consists of categorizing and sub-categorize samples; Also Ernes in same years explained that the information from data could change year by year. The analysis goes on the reasons for abandoning education not depending on lack of infrastructure; lack of teachers or low revenue of families; but other factors that are not to be neglected by country authorities and its partners. The fields of our investigation are:

The national results for high school exams graduation (a lot of failure) The life after finishing university have Diploma (working market saturate) National politic to help youngers and student having university diploma unclearly Budget for national education (very low only 10%)

Table 1 High school Examination Result for Seven Years (2018 to 2024)

Years	Number of Candidate Taked Exams	Number of Candidats Admission	Number of Female Candidates	Number of Failure Candidates	Percentages
2018	77560	19 669	6389		25.36%
2019	90050	21959	6389		23.97%
2020	87632	38931	13387		44.43%
2021	77 560	19669	6389		25.36%
2022	101 601	8731	2093		9.37%
2023	93 468	25668	8442		27.46%
2024	93 835	20 660	7235		24.46%
Total	621 706	155 287	50 784	466419	22.77%

➤ Graphic of high School Pupils Result for Seven years

Graph 1 Graphic of high School Pupils Result for Seven years

GIT is appeared in this graphic, that the number of candidates who taked exam for is going up by contrast the number of admissions for bachelor diploma is going down. If we make subtraction between who get admission for bachelor and who fail (621 706 -155 287) = 466419; we got a difference of 466419 young who meet an embarrassment

situation; the number of girls who have admission is not moving up. This mass failure is depending on some factors Region of Kankan in sort time. In 2024, the number of candidates for bachelor examination of Kankan region is 12255 with its provinces.

N°1 Table 2 Shows Number of Candidate for high Schools Examination Kankan Province for the last three years

Years	Number of candidate	Number of admission	Number of failure
2024	5522	669	4853
2023	5521	667	4854
2022	5376	450	4926
Total	16419	1786	14633

N°1 Grap 2 Shows Number of Candidate for Bachelor Admission and Failure

N°2 Table 3 Shows Number of high schools Candidate, rate Admission and failure in Siguirri Province from 2021 to 2024

Years	Number of Candidate	Number of Girls	Rate of Admission	Number of Candidate Failure	Rate of Fail
2024	5152	1405	10,91%	4585	89,9%
2023	6035	1949	10,01%	5431,5	90%
2022	7194		24,10%	5467	76%
2021	4788	1244	9%	4788	91%
Total	23169		13%	20271,5	87%

N°2 Grap 3 Shows Candidate Number for Candidate and rate of Admission and Failure in Siguirri

In 2022, in another province in upper Guinea Kouroussa, the number of high school candidates was 4000, and only 500 got admission; However, in 2024 5522 candidates, 667 have admission.

➤ *Why this Mass Failure of Candidates?*

I think that there are some factors for that; we made a shortlist

- Teachers Fewer qualifications and less motivated
- Less Infrastructures and not adequate
- Budget allocation of only 10% is very low
- Political strategy changes all the time; not continuity; each new Government makes a new strategy different from who it replaced
- Less pedagogical materials
- Families are less involved
- Learners are not encouraging

➤ *What can be done shortly for those failing in the Bachelor Examination?*

- *Schools' Boys and Girls are in the Embarrassed Situation that;*

They should not beThe number of candidates failed each year is huge and staying at home or in bars for a long time not doing anything, finally, they forget and again fall into the illiteracy Students who had been admitted by a specialist they didn't want, or universities where they were not sent, resign easily because of lack of financial support; many of them abandon for lack of financial support, which constitutes other sources of abandoning education

- *Graduation Outlive when they got a Diploma;*

Any help they should have been not done and they go straightway on unemployment A sample of 150 resident in the area have been asked about their level of education. In the Graphic shows the different levels in the sample

Grap 4 Level of education

N°3 Table 4 Reasons of leaving schools

Reasons	Sample	Frequency in Percentage
No Answers	16	10,66%
Lack of infrastructures	45	30%
Lack of teachers	55	36,66%
Poor revenue of families	34	22,66%

The high level of illiteracy is confirmed in the table above, the central government and its partners have to do more to improve communities' access to social infrastructures and to provide teachers for communities.

The level of Illiteracy is around 80%. The reasons given for this very high rate include the lack of infrastructure, teachers, and the low revenue of many families to support school fees. so young people are attracted to artisanal mining. This high level of illiteracy and the students involved in the delinquency are due to loss of basic qualifications.

Grap 5 Demonstration of the delinquency
Source: Survey in the field (kintinian 2017) kk

Due to the lack of better-functioning security systems, the crime rate is very high in Siguiri, Kintinian, and causes many social problems as shown above. The lack of security and other social problems are bad governance in the area.

The impact of leaving schools on younger juveniles is demonstrated across levels of education the demonstration of delinquency, which is shown in the table

Table 5 Level of Education is crossed to demonstration of Delinquency

Level of Education//Delinquency	Illiterate	Primary	Secondary	Professional	University	Total
No answer	12	0	6	1	1	22
Alcoholism	74	9	11	0	4	98
use drugs	6	0	3	1	0	10
Prostitution	37	2	7	0	2	48
Rape	22	5	2	0	0	29
Murder	18	2	2	0	1	23
leave families	17	3	3	1	2	26
Steal.	2	0	0	0	0	2

Source: Survey field Investigations (kintinian 2017) kk

This tableau the correlation it is shown that more illiterate secondary University levels are deeply involved in delinquency, which is demonstrated by the number of alcoholism (higher) indicate in the column of Illiterate, using drugs, rape, prostitution, and abandoning families (generally for Ladies already got married) and the rate of murder increased. It is being pointed out that: Alcoholism (74/98) 75,51%, Prostitution (37/48) 77,08%, Rape (22/29) 75,86%, Murder (18/23)78,26%, Leave families (17/26) 65,38%, are Illiterate;

When we compare the among of 98 respondents for alcoholism 74 are illiterate 9 primary level, 11 secondary and 4 University level. There is an urgent need for school infrastructures to reduce the rate of Illiteracy.24 residents in the sample are in the education program; by deduction, these junior high schools are going to fall in the school attainment

N°3 Table 6 Transpose level of education on delinquency in term of percentage. (Analysis of data)

Level of Education/Delinquency	Illiterate
No answer	14,70%
Alcoholism	65,30%
Use drugs	6,70%
Prostitution	32,00%
Rape	19,30%
Murder	15,30%
Leave families	17,30%
Steal.	1,30%

Source: Survey in the field (kintinian 2017) kk

The high rate of delinquency is significantly linked to illiteracy and bad education programs which could cause them to leave educations.

➤ *Implementations*

In this section, we make observations and recommendations for the future study of school attendance in light of the changing world and educational landscape noted in the previous section. Mass failure of candidates for the high school degree exam; and the presence of traditional mining can be a cause of motivation to abandon schools with no basic qualifications and why.

- Retake exam
- Attract by artisanal mining; the second could be more attractive
- Follow the immigration process; hoping that could change their social statute

The national politics to insert on the working market or help them to get a job is not carried out; that is justified by the number of the candidates who fail in the degree examination. Some additional factors could increase the causes of motivation for students to end education program with no qualification. Mass failure of degree candidates; which is increasing each year. Outlive by comparing that who get admission for high school degree diploma; always depending families over 25 years which is a shame. Sectorial political government has to insert in the working market who have been graduates not Cleared.

➤ *Summary*

There are too many exams. In the Guinea education program; despite of some progress in Guinea's education sector; many challenges are still underway such as lack of infrastructure and adequate teachers' qualifications; sectorial politics; budget for education; Insert programs for the graduates into the working work force. We suggest maintaining the same criteria of admissions for Junior high Schools from 10/20 to 20/20 to get a passing for Junior High school graduation. By contrast, a candidate who takes an examination but does not get the mark required; but has 9 marks and 8;5 should have admission for professional study. This group could be divided into two categories

- The candidate who got 9 marks should have an admission for the level A in the professional schools (three years of education)
- The candidate who got from 8.99 to 8.50 or 8;00 should have been admitted for level B (two years of education professional to learn different trades like; carpenter; masonry work; electrician; plumbing etc...)
- The exam organized each year to have admission for professional education should be canceled. The diploma for two categories has to be different from the bachelor's diploma.

The advantages of these are that the government could save money that is used to organize each year's examination to have admission for professional education that money can be used to build adequate infrastructures; improve the education environment and good pay for teachers. It can contribute to: Reduce the number of abandoned schools. Reduce the number of candidates for immigration and reduce the number of traditional mining activities. Reduce the rate of failure of high school exams. Increase labor forces in the working market and give hope to school boys and girls.

The Government must take a strong decision to make schools compulsory for young people to go to schools until 20 years of age or to follow training courses over 20 of age. The disadvantage of this if any measure is not taken, is an investment from parents in children from an earlier age and the investment done by the government cannot be returned "No return back investment on the pupils" if it is not stopped down.

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